

ONE YEAR OF “BY JHOVE! EXPLAIN YOURSELF!”

Micky Lindlar

TIB Leibniz Information
Centre for Science and
Technology
Germany
micky.lindlar@tib.eu
0000-0003-3709-5608

Lotte Wijsman

National Archives of the
Netherlands
Netherlands
lotte.wijsman@nationaal
chief.nl
0009-0009-2707-5014

Georgia Moppet

Open Preservation
Foundation
United Kingdom
georgia.moppett@openpres
ervation.org
0009-0008-1004-824X

Abstract - JHOVE is one of the most widely used tools in digital preservation, but anyone who uses it will be familiar with the various difficulties that follow. Causes of these problems vary, ranging from not understanding the impact of validation errors to outdated training materials to a graphical user interface (GUI) considered not user-friendly. “By JHOVE! Explain Yourself!” is a Special Interest Group (SIG) hosted by the maintainer of JHOVE, the Open Preservation Foundation (OPF), and co-chaired by the authors of the poster. It brings together members of the OPF as well as interested parties within the digital preservation community who are interested in evolving JHOVE and discussing their issues with peers.

Following a Birds-of-a-Feather meeting at iPRES2024, which collected input for the SIG, this poster will present results of the first year of the working group.

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Conference Topics - Tūhono - Connect.

I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

JHOVE is one of the most widely used tools in digital preservation, but organisations who use it will be familiar with its various difficulties. How can these be best addressed?

When using JHOVE for file format validation, you receive multiple error messages. Currently, JHOVE supports different types of responses, from error messages for validation failures - which can indicate a problem with the file - to info messages covering everything else in the reports, e.g. too many PDF fonts for reporting. But even validation errors come

in many shapes and forms, especially for complex file formats like PDF.

Several members of the Open Preservation Foundation have wanted a shared space to better connect and collaborate on these issues since the [December '22 OPF Advisory Group](#).

A Special Interest Group (SIG) was created, - named “By JHOVE! Explain Yourself!” by its attendees - and inspired by the following aims: to improve documentation and understandability, enable the community to handle errors better, develop a searchable registry and improve the tool by identifying bugs. Additionally, the group works on the user-friendliness of the tool and the documentation to help people get started. Importantly, no development expertise is required to join, as our efforts for this past year have targeted general, global users and not developers.

II. KICK-OFF AT IPRES2024

At iPRES2024 in Ghent, the JHOVE workshop “Validation Anonymous: A JHOVE Error Message Helpspace” [1] and a Birds-of-a-Feather (BoF) “Gettin' SIG-y with it: a JHOVE Special Interest Group to enhance documentation and explain error messages” [2] were held. The results and feedback of the workshop and the BoF helped shape the modus operandi of the working group. As part of the “Validation Anonymous” workshop a template for describing error message analysis was tested. The template is based on a methodology presented at iPRES2024 [3]. Feedback given during the workshop was incorporated into a second version of the

template, which has been used by the By JHOVE! SIG since. The BoF session was intended to gather feedback on the planned direction of the SIG. As such, attendees were invited to comment directly on plans for the three SIG pillars “Errors and Warning”, “Usability” and “Documentation”. Clear outcomes from the BoF session included the need for a centralised location to find anything about JHOVE, the need to improve the JHOVE wiki entries for errors and warnings – in particular for the many errors that are currently labelled “needs review”, to wish to have more graphical schemas and explanations, and, lastly, the wish for a forum for discussions for the general user base.

III. WORK MODUS OF THE SPECIAL INTEREST GROUP

The By JHOVE! SIG officially kicked off on October 1st 2024. The group meets once a month for one hour online. Every third meeting (“quarterly meeting”) is dedicated to presentations on how different organisations integrate JHOVE into their workflows, how they approach error handling, or what additional tools they have developed to handle and manage validation output. Presentations in these “quarterly” calls so far have included a presentation by CSC on their File Scraper [4] tool and how it integrates JHOVE or a presentation on workflows for file format identification and validation error treatment at Digital Archives Flanders.

The “regular” meetings are not run in plenary. Instead, there is a 5 minute intro, which welcomes new members and introduces the breakout groups. The breakout groups then run for 45 minutes and cover different topics from one of the SIGs three core pillars: “Errors and Warnings”, “Documentation” and “Usability”. Members of the group can suggest new themes for breakout groups through a spreadsheet, which is also used to track the status of these topics/tasks. The poster will include an overview of how this information is captured in the spreadsheet, how it links to other structured information such as the error and warnings documentation sheets and how the work plan is derived from it.

IV. RESULTS OF THE FIRST YEAR

In addition to the description of the modus operandi as described above, the poster will showcase the results of the first year of the By JHOVE! SIG. The results will be presented in a quantitative way (number of different break-out groups, number

of different topics, documentation/wiki-pages updated as results of the SIG work) as well as examples for work on the different pillars. For Errors and Warnings the work will be described using the TIFF-HUL Error “Count mismatch for tag <tag>; expecting <minCount>, saw <count>”, which has been worked on extensively, resulting in improved documentation. For the “Documentation” pillar, the work on the “Getting Started Guide (Beginner)” will be showcased. For the “Usability” pillar first thoughts towards an improved GUI will be presented.

V. WHAT'S NEXT?

In addition to work completed during the first year of the SIG, the poster will include plans for future work. The authors believe that the poster presentation at iPRES will be an excellent opportunity to engage in wider audience discussion around the work on JHOVE. Feedback gathered at iPRES2025 will be incorporated into the future work of the SIG and we will hopefully manage to get a wider interest in the Asia - Pacific regions of the world, which are currently underrepresented in the SIG.

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Micky Lindlar leads the Digital Preservation Team at TIB. Serving as a director on the OPF Board since 2012, Micky has a special interest in the advancement of file format validation and OPF's role in this. Micky talks too much about PDF – on and off the job.

Lotte Wijsman is the Preservation Researcher at the National Archives of the Netherlands. Her work spans projects on significant properties, environmental sustainability, Flash content in web archives, and social media archiving. She also co-organizes the Bits and Bots study group, which empowers archivists with digital skills.

Georgia Moppet is the Community and Content officer at the Open Preservation Foundation, a non profit which provides expertise and support, empowering the digital preservation community to develop sustainable resources.

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